

BERYLLIUM FLUORIDES. PART III. HYDROLYSIS OF BERYLLIUM FLUORIDE

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From conductometric and thermometric titrations beryllium fluoride has been found to be hydrolysed by NaOH as follows :

The reaction mechanism of equation (1) has been confirmed by chemical analysis of the products of reaction taking place at the reacting ratio of 1:1, and by conductometric titration of beryllium fluoride by baryta. In the latter case the reaction takes place as :

Beryllium fluoride has also been found to be hydrolysed by carbonates, bicarbonates, nitrites, ammonia, and ethylenediamine with the precipitation of probably basic carbonate or hydroxide according to the case.

Aqueous solutions of beryllium fluoride have been known to be acidic suggesting the formation of an acid by hydrolysis of the fluoride. Tananaev and Deichman (*Bull. Acad. Sci. U.R.S.S., Classe Sci. Chim.*, 1947, 591) and Linnell and Haendler (*J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1948, 52, 819) showed that the pH of beryllium fluoride solutions dropped with its increasing concentration.

From potentiometric titration of a solution of beryllium sulphate by caustic alkali, Britton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2121) observed no precipitation even when one mole of alkali per mole of BeSO_4 was added, and attributed this to the formation of basic beryllium cations. Prytz (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1929, 180, 355) confirmed Britton's observation by similar titrations. During potentiometric and conductometric titrations of beryllium fluoride by sodium hydroxide, Prytz (*ibid.*, 1937, 231, 238) observed that a precipitate was formed immediately on passing the neutral point, and conductance increased sharply with addition of NaOH; he attributed the precipitation to decrease in the solubility of beryllium fluoride, however, without any experimental evidence. As beryllium fluoride is known to be very highly soluble and is not crystallisable, the observation by Prytz requires reinvestigation.

The present author has studied the hydrolysis of beryllium fluoride conductometrically and potentiometrically utilising caustic soda, baryta, alkali carbonate and bicarbonate as the titrants, and also by chemical analysis of the products of the reaction occurring at the ratio $\text{BeF}_2 : \text{NaOH} = 1 : 1$.

EXPERIMENTAL

The same potassium tetrafluoberyllate and beryllium fluoride, used previously, were utilised, and standardised as before (Sengupta, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 291). Other reagents were of analytical grade.

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The apparatuses used were the same as in the previous work (*loc. cit.*). The conductometric titrations of beryllium fluoride (Fig. 1) by caustic soda (curves I and II), baryta (curve IV), sodium carbonate, sodium and potassium bicarbonates (*vide* Discussion), and of potassium tetrafluoberyllate by barium chloride (curve III) were performed at a constant volume. For these titrations, sets of individual mixtures were prepared in wax-coated test tubes by mixing equal volumes of a standard beryllium fluoride solution with calculated volumes of water, and finally adding increasing volumes of a titrant. For preparing the solutions for titration with baryta, freshly boiled and cooled distilled water was particularly utilised. The test tubes were stoppered with waxed rubber stoppers immediately after the addition of the last reagent. The conductance of the mixtures was measured the next day.

FIG. 1

- Curve I. 3 c.c. beryllium fluoride (0.1843 *M*) titrated by NaOH (0.7747 *M*) at constant volume (25 c.c.).
 Curve II. 5 c.c. of the above titrated by NaOH (0.1529 *M*) at constant volume (25 c.c.).
 Curve III. 10 c.c. K_2BeF_4 (0.01 *M*) titrated by barium chloride (0.02 *M*) at constant volume (20 c.c.).
 Curve IV. 1 c.c. beryllium fluoride (0.2793 *M*) titrated at constant volume (30 c.c.) by baryta (0.02977 *M*).

FIG. 2

- Curve I. Thermometric titrations of 100 c.c. beryllium fluoride (0.03317 *M*) by NaOH (1.020 *N*).
 Curve II. 100 c.c. beryllium fluoride (0.0838 *N*) by NaOH (1.104 *N*).

The results of thermometric titration of beryllium fluoride by caustic soda have been shown in Fig. 2 after subtracting the values recorded in the blank titrations (Fig. 3), which were performed by adding the caustic soda solutions utilised in the above experiments to water. In a similar way thermometric titrations of beryllium fluoride by sodium carbonate, and sodium and potassium bicarbonates were carried out (*vide* Discussion).

In order to carry out chemical analysis of the products of reaction occurring at $BeF_2 : NaOH = 1:1$, 40 c.c. of BeF_2 (0.1618 *M*), containing 58.2 mg. beryllium and 246 mg. fluorine, was taken in a beaker. To it caustic soda (0.1070 *N*; 60.5 c.c.) was added dropwise whilst the solution

was constantly stirred. Gelatinous precipitate was found to appear. To the solution paper pulp was added, and the solution was filtered (I) by suction through a paper pulp pad. The residual precipitate was transferred to the filter with the help of a quantitative filter paper. The precipitate (p_1) was drained thoroughly and was transferred into a platinum crucible; a small amount of sodium carbonate solution was added to it, and the whole was dried carefully. The paper along

FIG. 3

Thermometric blank titrations of (i) 100 c.c. water by NaOH (1.020 N), and (ii) 100 c.c. water by NaOH (1.104 N).

amount of beryllium was estimated in this residue, and found to be 24.8 mg.

The amounts of beryllium distributed in the precipitate (p_1) and the filtrate (f_1) were thus found to be 1.34 : 1 instead of the presumed 1:1 ratio according to equation (1) (*vide Discussion*). The higher amount of beryllium in the precipitate was evidently due to the adsorption of beryllium from the filtrate in the filtering pad, indicated by the amount of fluorine (26.5 mg.) found in it (*vide supra*). Thus, almost all of the fluorine, (246 - 26.5) mg., was found in the filtrate (f_1), and therefore the ratio of Be : F in the filtrate was approximately 1 : 4, showing the presence of tetrafluoberyllate in the filtrate.

DISCUSSION

Conductometric titration of beryllium fluoride by caustic soda reveals one inflection point in the curves (curves I and II, Fig. 1) corresponding to the ratio of $\text{BeF}_2 : \text{NaOH} = 1 : 1$ (not well pronounced) and 1 : 2. As gelatinous precipitate has been noticed almost from the beginning of the titration, the reactions are presumed to be :

The thermometric titrations of beryllium fluoride by caustic soda (curves I and II, Fig. 2) also indicate the inflection points at the above ratios of BeF_2 and NaOH. As before, gelatinous precipitate was noticed in the titration vessel, indicating the reactions to occur according to equations (1) and (2). These reaction mechanisms have been confirmed by conductometric titration of beryllium fluoride by baryta when only one break is noticed in the titration curve (curve IV, Fig. 1) corresponding to $\text{BeF}_2 : \text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2 = 2 : 1$, indicating the following reaction to occur :

since barium fluoberyllate and beryllium hydroxide are practically insoluble. The quantitative precipitation of tetrafluoberyllate ion by barium ion was confirmed by titrating a potassium tetrafluoberyllate solution with barium chloride (curve III, Fig. 1). The reaction mechanism occurring

according to equation (1) was also corroborated by chemical analysis of the products of reaction taking place at the reacting ratio of $\text{BeF}_2 : \text{NaOH} = 1 : 1$, when beryllium was found to be distributed approximately in equimolar portions in the precipitate and the filtrate, and the ratio of Be : F in the filtrate found to be 1 : 4, indicating the presence of tetrafluoberyllate ion in it (*vide supra*). That the hydrolytic reaction of tetrafluoberyllate ion occurs according to equation (2) has been shown in a previous communication (Sen Gupta, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 433). The above experimental facts show that the action of NaOH on BeF_2 solution leads to a continuous separation of $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$, because the complex BeF_4^{2-} ion that might be formed in course of the reaction, as indicated by titration with baryta, is not strong enough to mask appreciably the usual reaction of Be^{2+} ion in solution. Thus the assumption of Prytz (*loc. cit.*) about the hydrolytic reaction of beryllium fluoride by caustic soda is found not to hold good.

It was noticed that in both the conductometric titrations utilising alkali carbonate or bicarbonate, the conductance increased gradually with no definite inflection point in the curves. It was further observed with the bicarbonates that the stoppers of the test tubes were ejected out immediately after mixing the reactants, which indicated the generation of carbon dioxide in the reaction between beryllium fluoride and a bicarbonate. Gelatinous precipitate was found in the test tubes where sodium carbonate had been utilised, but in the case of bicarbonates a very small amount of precipitate in some of the test tubes was observed, and no precipitate in the test tubes where the proportion of bicarbonate was very great in comparison to the beryllium fluoride taken.

In the case of thermometric titrations, at the end of experiments gelatinous precipitates were noticed in the Dewar flask when alkali carbonate was utilised, but no precipitate in the case of bicarbonates. These titrations indicate that sodium carbonate hydrolyses beryllium fluoride with the precipitation, probably, of basic beryllium carbonate, whilst alkali bicarbonates also hydrolyse it with the production, probably, of alkali beryllium tetrafluoride and basic beryllium carbonate at lower bicarbonate concentrations, but soluble complex beryllium carbonate ions at higher concentrations of bicarbonate.

On addition of sodium nitrite to a beryllium fluoride solution, nitrous fumes evolved and beryllium hydroxide separated out. On adding ammonia or ethylenediamine to a beryllium fluoride solution, beryllium hydroxide was precipitated. These reactions also lead to the hydrolysis of beryllium fluoride. On adding a comparatively weak base, like pyridine, no precipitate of beryllium hydroxide was noticed, and by evaporation of the residual mixture, no substance could be crystallised out.

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